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An Empirical Analysis to Investigate the Influence of 5A's on the Tourists Satisfaction to the Celebration of Banatu Festival in the Philippines

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Abstract

In Cabanatuan City, the most progressive city in Nueva Ecija celebrated their festival every first week of January with a five-day celebration wrapped around the first ever “Banatu Festival,” which showcased the history, culture, talent, beauty and creativity of local folks. It is important to determine the satisfaction of tourists as it is one of the leading factors which assists to deal with the competitiveness of the tourism industry where the festival arranged. The general objectives of this study are to assess tourist satisfaction and to identify problems with the 5A's which could have feasible solutions in order to provide a development strategy for the Philippine Banatu Festival celebrations. This study utilized a descriptive research design with quantitative approach and with help of ready-made questionnaire in gathering all information to investigate the tourists' satisfaction using 5A's on the celebration of Banatu Festival. This study was conducted at Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, where the respondents are identified. The respondents of this study came from the tourist of Banatu Festival to give the researchers enough data to find out the result. Statistical tools such as Percentage, Frequency Distribution, and Weighted Mean were used in analyzing the data gathered. Majority of the respondents were female, the age range of most of the respondents is between 15-24 years old. Most of the respondents agreed that the accommodation was adequate, safe, and provided the best conditions for the event. It is recommended to pursue the activities that bring entertainment to the tourist. Moreover, the researchers recommended to initiate events or activities that suitable for all ages including teenagers and children.

Keywords: 5A's of Tourism, Satisfaction, Banatu Festival

Introduction

A festival is known to most people as a day of celebration or festivities. s (1987) defines a festival as an event, a social phenomenon, encountered in virtually all human cultures. The colorful variety and dramatic intensity of its dynamic choreographic and aesthetic aspects, the signs of deep meaning underlying them, its historical roots, and the involvement of the “natives” have always attracted the attention of casual visitors, have consumed travelers and men of letters alike. Furthermore, Falassi explained that festivals in the social sciences are simply taken from common language, where the term covers a constellation of very different events, sacred and profane, private and public, sanctioning tradition and introducing innovation, proposing nostalgic revivals, providing the expressive means for the survival of the most archaic folk customs, and celebrating the highly speculative and experimental avant-gardes of the elite fine arts.

Festivals are being held for a variety of causes, since the interest in planning them has grown in recent years in many locations. From a tourism standpoint, a special event is brief and has a significant influence on the host region in terms of, for instance. A greater awareness of and a more favorable perception of the city or region may result from increased tourism numbers, visitor spending, and publicity. There are many festivals celebrated throughout the world and the Philippines is no exception. Often, a province, town, or municipality

celebrates a festival in the Philippines. A festival is viewed by the researchers as a means of sharing the history, identity and values of the place and people to others and the younger generations. A festival is also a way to attract visitors to come to the province, town or municipality therefore a festival has an impact on the hosting place. The impact may be good or bad but none the less a festival has an impact. Since festivals are celebrated throughout the world it is very important to learn, understand, and measure its impacts on the hosting community.

In Cabanatuan City, the most progressive city in Nueva Ecija celebrated their festival every first week of January with a five-day celebration wrapped around the first ever “Banatu Festival,” which showcased the history, culture, talent, beauty and creativity of local folks. This year’s celebration of the so-called Banatu Festival 2023 carries the theme “Bagong Sigla at Pag-Asa ng Isang Lungsod na Nagkakaisa.” The activities include the two-night Sayaw Cabanatuan (Jan. 27 and 28), DepEd Night for the City Schools Division (Jan. 29), Barangay and SK Night (Jan. 30) celebration of Holy Mass, opening program for Banatu Festival and Ginoong Tricycle Driver 2023 (Jan. 31), Wellness Check Up by the city health office and Ms. Gay Cabanatuan Coronation Night (Feb. 1), Pet Day by city veterinary office and Bb. Cabanatuan 2023 Coronation Night (Feb. 2), Longganisa Festival and Araw ng Magsasaka, Zumbang Gabi and Gawad Parangal (Feb. 3). The whole week of celebration of the festival was enjoyed by the tourist from different places.

Festivals as a part of tourism, it is important to determine the satisfaction of tourists as it is one of the leading factors which assists to deal with the competitiveness of the tourism industry where the festival arranged (Meng et al, 2008). When evaluating the tourist satisfaction, a priority should be given to the factor, Accommodation, Amenities, Attractions, Activities and Accessibility. It is one of the reasons why local tourism is growing; tourists who experienced these festivals keep coming back to see more. Popular festivals attract millions of tourists and have become a major source of income for some areas.

Thus, the general objectives of this study are to assess tourist satisfaction and to identify problems with the 5A's which could have feasible solutions in order to provide a development strategy for the Philippine Banatu Festival celebrations.

Specifically, the researchers aim to investigate the influence of 5A's on the tourists' satisfaction to the celebration of Banatu Festival.

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. How may the profile of the tourists be described?
2. How may the tourists' satisfaction be assessed?
3. What are the problems encountered by the tourists during the celebration of Banatu Festival?
4. What tourism enhancement plan may be proposed to address the problems of the respondents?

Festival

Festivals are instruments for tourism and culture development branding (Palupi et al., 2019 Gusti et al., 2021; Hastuti, 2005; Balirwa & Waholi, 2019). The festivals are carefully planned to create the appropriate "first impression" to make a place an acceptable tourist destination (Bulu et al., 2020 ; Soleha et al., 2020). Some festivals are clone to commemorate events in history (Soleha et al.,2020)or show gratitude's for good harvest ((Valck et al., 2021; Palupi et al., 2019:Bakhtiar et al., 2020). Festivals in the Philippines are celebrated to boost tourism and attract tourists. In the Philippines, people love big and colorful celebrations that mark their culture and homage to history, religion, and customs. As the country's tourism slogan says, it's really “more fun in the Philippines” tourists from all over the world and even local tourists, travel around the Philippines not just to experience its beaches and picture sights, but also to catch the country's greatest festival that can give new meaning to merriment, feasting, music, dancing, and colorful parades.

In Nueva Ecija there are numerous festival that are being celebrated. Those Festivals are events, a social phenomenon, encountered in virtually all human cultures. The colorful variety and dramatic intensity of its dynamic choreographic and aesthetic aspects, the signs of deep meaning underlying them, its historical roots, and the involvement of the o'natives" have always attracted the attention of casual visitors, have consumed travelers and men of letters alike.

Therefore, festival shows as an expressive way to celebrate glorious heritage, culture, and traditions. They are meant to rejoice special moments and emotions in our lives with our loved ones. They play as an important role to add structure to our social lives and connect us with our families and backgrounds. They give us a distraction from our day to day, exhausting routine of life, and give us some inspiration to remember the important things and moments in life. Festivals were started to pass the legends, knowledge, and traditions onto the next generation.

Tourism

Tourism as a product and service-oriented industry, could generate widespread benefits and impacts to the economy and society. It could contribute to the achievement of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) particularly those concerning poverty alleviation, environmental conservation, and generation of employment opportunities for women, indigenous communities, and young people. Further, tourism could be a source of revenue (foreign exchange earnings, tax revenue) to the government and because of its multiplier effect, could provide opportunities for local economic development (LED). The direct, upstream, and downstream industries involved in tourism activities have the potential for creating sectorial linkages and economic opportunities in the localities.

Nowadays, tourism is a part of the infrastructure of any country's economy the growth and development of tourism is of great importance. Tourism is one of the most profitable and lucrative industries, which create a bastion of economical (fiscal growth), private business, society, and human resources, direct and indirect, full-time, and seasonal employment growth. It continues to grow as a significant industry generating economic growth and development in the Philippines. Associated with its success is the participation of communities surrounding tourist destinations.

Tourism plays an important role in establishing a nation like in the Philippines and serves as one of the state's contributors. Lickorish and Jenkins (2007) stated that the government has often played a supporting but largely background role in the development of tourism, particularly in the developed countries. Further, Rodolfo (2009) cited as one of tourism's benefits is that the achievement of tourism development will heighten their national identity and sense of unity. According to Said (2008), tourist spots boasts environmental features that cater to ecotourism, maritime as well as community-based tourism, so steps must be taken to conserve its infrastructure and culture that can potentially be lost if no effort is made to protect such attractions.

Hence, Tourism offers great opportunities for emerging economies and developing countries. It creates jobs, strengthens the local economy, contributes to local infrastructure development, and can help to conserve the natural environment and cultural assets and traditions, and to reduce poverty and inequality.

Banatu Festival

According to the City Government of Cabanatuan, In the previous years, the Banatu Festival had been a tradition to call the annual fiesta as "Araw ng Cabanatuan". It had brought a lot of smiles to Cabanatuños but was never famous nor advertised nationwide.

Through the leadership of Mayor Julius Cesar V. Vergara together with the newly established City Information and Tourism Office, the committee decided to search for a more suitable name that can be compared to the Panagbenga of Baguio, Sinulog of Cebu, and Ati-atihan of Kalibo, Aklan - a word that would truly describe the growth and progress of Cabanatuan throughout the years, a word that will signify the rich history and prosperous future of the city. Lastly, a name for a festival that will not only bring joy to Cabanatuños but rather attract thousands of tourists from around the globe.

The Banatu is a type of vine that grows amidst struggling conditions. It is used as a binding rope for Baklads, Bunuhan and Palukso.

Just like the Banatu, Cabanatuan started as a small barrio in the town of Gapan. It may have faced a lot of challenges but through the efforts and "bayanihan" of its people, it has risen to be the center of economy of the province of Nueva Ecija.

Cabanatuan has become a sturdy pillar for national growth and advancement, and at present, the people are striving to be more self-reliant- harnessing all potentials as the city is endowed with considerable natural

resources; its farmlands are rich and productive; the people are imaginative and hardworking; and the Cabanatuan's spirit had remained firm and strong.

This research study focused on the celebration of Banatu Festival through survey in the participation of tourists using the 5A's of tourism.

5A's of Tourism

Dickman (1996) stated that Tourist Destination and Tourism Product is required to consist of 5 main elements or 5As as follows:

1. Attraction is a very important element as it attracts tourist to travel in such places. The tourist attractions can be classified as religious sites, beaches, mountains, national parks, festivals, or beautiful and unique places. Generally, the famous tourist attractions must have more than one attraction. For example, Phuket has various tourist attractions such as beaches, water activities, entertainment places including interesting architecture.
2. Accessibility means the convenience that make the tourists or travelers reach the places rapidly, safely, and conveniently. The tourist sites must provide the transportation system consisting of transportation routes, vehicles, and stations. The transport operators have the aim in transporting people and goods to the destinations.
3. Amenity means basic facilities and infrastructures for tourists such as public utilities, electricity, water supply, telephones, toilets and needed facilities for tourists such as hospitals, banks, post offices, and emergency services which are important as well.
4. Accommodation: The tourist sites should provide sufficient number of lodgings with the variety in prices and service provisions suitable for the places. Moreover, the lodges should not be located too far from the tourist sites.
5. Activity means what the tourists can do in the duration of rest and travel in such places to make the travel and rest time of the tourists more interesting. The activities should be various and match the demands of the tourists; for example, activities related to expenditures, marine activities such as scuba diving, swimming, etc.

Materials and Method

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design with quantitative approach and with help of ready-made questionnaire in gathering all information to investigate the tourists' satisfaction using 5A's on the celebration of Banatu Festival. According to Ary (2016) descriptive research portrays the researcher's plan to proceed to gain an understanding for some relevant aspects of the phenomena of interest from an individual, organizational, and industry-oriented perspective. It includes an accurate profile of persons, events, or situations.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, where the respondents are identified. The respondents of this study came from the tourist of Banatu Festival to give the researchers enough data to find out the result.

Respondents of the study

The respondents of this research are the selected tourists who attended the celebration of Banatu Festival in Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija in 2023 Celebration. After gathering the estimated number of tourist attendees of the said event from the Tourism of Cabanatuan City. With the aid of the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator, the study's target respondents were determined. This has a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. With a 50% response distribution and a total population of 625, the researchers arrive at 239 responders.

Sample and sampling procedure

The researchers used purposive sampling to collect the data needed. According to Patton (2015), purposive sampling is the subject selected because of some characteristics. The respondents of this study are the selected visitors of Banatu Festival in Cabanatuan City.

Research Instruments

The finding of this study conducted was through an online survey form, with the database can collect and store data, it also provides statistical software analysis of the findings. Survey research is the most fundamental tool for all quantitative outcome research methodologies and studies.

Survey questionnaires are a set of questions to accomplish the objectives of the study participants encourage to complete them over the internet via a google form. The online survey questionnaires constructed in the google form consisted of three parts. The first part contains the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part contains the variables that affect the tourists' satisfaction using the 5A's of tourism which is accommodation, amenities, attractions, accessibility, and activities and their satisfaction towards the festival. While the last part is consisting of questions to know the other variable that will affect the results of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research study entitled "An Empirical Analysis to Investigate the Influence of 5A's on the Tourists' Satisfaction to the Celebration of Banatu Festival in the Philippines" will be conducted by asking for approval of the school subject teacher of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, and the permission of the selected tourist of Banatu Festival which are the respondents of the study. The researchers will use survey questionnaires and interview as a research tool, which serves as a medium to collect data. This paper formulated semi-interview questions and survey questions that are depth analysis and focus group discussion to further describe and explore each variable and the topic.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data collected from the respondents was encoded, tallied, and analyzed. Statistical tools such as Percentage, Frequency Distribution, and Weighted Mean were used in analyzing the data gathered. The scale below was employed to interpret the result.

Table #1. Scales for Interpretation

Scale	Mean Range	Interpretation	Description
4	4.00-3.00	Strongly Agree	Highly In Favor
3	2.99-2.00	Agree	In Favor
2	1.99-1.00	Disagree	Highly Not in Favor
1	1.0-0.99	Strongly Disagree	Not In Favor

The table shows the factors by the researchers in the interpretation and description of data under the help of tourists during Banatu Festival. To determine the favorable using a 4-point Likert scale. The purpose of the researchers is to know the influence of 5A's on the tourists' satisfaction to the celebration of Banatu Festival in the Philippines. Aside from the said scale, the researcher used the following statistical tools to classify, tabulate, and analyze the data in connection with the objectives of the research study:

1. In describing the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, the researchers used frequency and percentage.
2. To investigate the influence of 5A's on the tourists' satisfaction with the celebration of Banatu Festival; the researchers employed a weighted mean and ranking.
3. In describing and analyzing the problems and possible solutions encountered by respondents during the celebration of Banatu Festival, the data was treated with frequency and percentage.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

1. Percentage Distribution of the respondent's profile variable

1.1 Percentage of the respondent's variable in terms of Sex.

Table #2 present the percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of Sex.

Table #2 Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	87	36%
Female	152	64%
Total	239	100%

The majority of the respondents were Female with the frequency of 152 or 64% of the total respondents. The results shows that female is more engaged in attending festivals events, it is because female find social interactions to be more rewarding than male.

According to LaTina Emerson (2019) Females find same-sex social interactions to be more rewarding than males, and females are more sensitive to the rewarding actions of oxytocin (OT) than males, according to a research study led by Georgia State University on the brain mechanisms that determine the rewarding properties of social interactions.

1.2 Percentage Distribution of the respondent’s profile variable in terms of Age.

Table #3 presents the percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of Age.

Table #3. Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-24 years old	186	78%
25-34 years old	33	14%
35-44 years old	8	3%
45-54 years old	10	4%
55-64 years old	2	1%
Total	239	100%

The distribution of age ranges of the respondents is presented in the table. Most of the respondents range from the age of **fifteen** (15) to **twenty-four** (24) years old. The results indicate that many teens or adolescents are in the phase of their lives whereas they are going out for entertainment, learning, and socializing with their peers.

As stated by United Nations, there is no universally agreed international definition of the youth age group. For statistical purposes, however, the United Nations—without prejudice to any other definitions made by Member States—defines ‘youth’ as those persons between the ages of 15 and 24 years who's more engaged in going out with friends for entertainment.

2. Investigate the satisfaction of the tourist on the Celebration of Banatu Festival using the 5A’s of Tourism.

2.1 Investigating the Tourist Satisfaction of the tourist in terms of Accommodation.

Table #4 Presenting tourist satisfaction in terms of Accommodation.

Accommodation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Verbal Description
Enough accommodations around the destination.	3.00	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Accommodation prices are affordable.	2.8	Agee	2	In favor
Facilities in accommodations are in the best condition.	3.00	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Accommodation is safe and secure.	3.00	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Average Weighted Mean	2.95			In favor

Table #4 shows the overall tourist satisfaction of the respondents in terms of accommodation, it has a weighted mean of **2.95**. The enough, secured, safe, and the best condition of accommodation got the highest weighted

mean of 3.00 as the verbal interpretation of “**Strongly agree**”. However, the “accommodation prices are affordable” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.8 and interpreted as “**Agree**”.

The results convey that the respondents on the day of the celebration are well accommodate by the hotels or facilities where they stay after the celebration and spent the night. The hotels and facilities meet the needs of the respondents who need accommodation overnight or longer.

According to Akyeampong (2007) tourist accommodation as an establishment which offers its facilities and services to individuals or groups. Examples include, but are not limited to hotels, motels, guesthouses, and company apartments/chalets. However, in its entirety, it can be defined as any facility that provides a psychological base for tourists or individuals who are temporarily away from their usual place of residence or work (Mensah et al, 2013). Basically, bedrooms are the primary products that accommodation facilities offer to their clients. This, notwithstanding, a host of other facilities and services offered for sale include restaurants and bars (food and beverage), recreational amenities (swimming pools, tennis courts, horse riding), health facilities (spas) and conference and meeting facilities among others for use by visitors. In modern times, accommodation facilities place great emphasis on conferencing and meetings as a result of the growth in business tourism.

2.2 Investigating the Tourist Satisfaction of the tourist in terms of Amenities.

Table #5 Presenting tourist satisfaction in terms of Amenities.

Amenities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Verbal Description
Proper sanitary facilities in destination.	2.94	Agree	3	In favor
Ample parking spaces in destination.	2.71	Agree	4	In favor
ATM facilities are available around the destination.	2.97	Agree	2	In favor
Proper medical treatments and other.	3.10	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Average Weighted Mean	2.93			In favor

The overall satisfaction of the respondents in amenities has a weighted mean of **2.93**. The table shows that proper medical treatments got the highest weighted mean of 3.10 verbally interpreted as “**Strongly Agree**”. In comparison to “Ample parking spaces in destination” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.71 as the verbal interpretation of “**Agree**”.

This demonstrate that during the celebration of Banatu Festival, the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Cabanatuan City prepared and paid attention on giving proper medical service during the celebration if something unexpected event happens.

One of the most common problems with large-scale events such as festivals is inadequate medical services and facilities. Without these, attendees won’t be able to get the aid they need if an emergency arises. It could cause tragic outcomes. According to Khalid A. (2013), Health care providers need to be aware of the health hazards that are prone to occur in festivals to be able to manage them effectively. They also need to be aware of the types of festivals, habits, and traditions done of the majority or minorities residing in their area so that they expect the potential health problems and ready to deal with them. Health authorities should initiate a targeted health education program and campaign to alert the people about expected hazards, before each occasion, with advice and instructions on how to avoid them. The hospitals should be properly staffed and equipped before each festival and be vigilant for the risk of mass accidents.

2.3 Investigating the Tourist Satisfaction of the tourist in terms of Attraction.

Table #6 Presenting tourist satisfaction in terms of Attraction.

Attraction	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Verbal Description
Natural attraction in destination.	3.12	Strongly Agree	3.5	Highly in favor
Cultural attraction in destination.	3.12	Strongly Agree	3.5	Highly in favor
People who live in destination are warm welcoming.	3.18	Strongly Agree	2	Highly in favor
Variety of food and beverages in destination.	3.28	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Average Weighted Mean	3.17			Highly in favor

The overall satisfaction of the respondents in attractions is 3.17 verbally interpreted as “**Strongly Agree.**” Among the items cited, the variety of food and beverages in destination got the highest **weighted mean of 3.17** with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree, while cultural and natural attraction in destination both got the lowest weighted mean of 3.12 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The results indicates that there are variety of food and beverage that the respondents can choose from during the celebration of Banatu Festival. The said event location has a diversity of food offered by the locals that motivates tourist to visit the destination.

Historically speaking, because food has been a key attraction for travelers, many destinations have tried to offer special culinary experiences to tourists (Cohen et al., 2004; Tsai et al, 2017). Local food can enhance the image of a destination because it is a representation of national, regional, and personal identities (Bessière,1998). Exploring how the use of local foods contributes to the value of tourist food consumption is an important issue, because it helps to understand tourists’ perceptions of a destination and to predict their future behaviors (Choe et al., 2018). Quan et al., 2004 believe that people today are open to the experience of consuming a variety of foods, which is a factor that inspires their travel plans (Cheng et al, 2015). To promote their local food, tourism marketers must determine every possible strategy for improving the value of tourists’ local food consumption (Choe et al.,)

Investigating the Tourist Satisfaction of the tourist in terms of Accessibility.

Table #7 Presenting tourist satisfaction in terms of **Accessibility.**

Accessibility	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Verbal Description
Good road network to reach the destination.	2.80	Agree	3	In favor
Travelling cost is affordable.	2.67	Agree	4	In favor
Adequate information and documents about the destination are available.	3.00	Strongly Agree	2	Highly in favor
You can reach the destination without traffic congestions.	2.57	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
Average Weighted Mean	2.94			In favor

The overall satisfaction of the respondents in terms of accessibility is **2.94** as the verbal description of “**In favor**”. Among the cited items, reaching the destination without traffic congestions got the highest weighted mean of 3.27 verbally interpreted as “strongly agree”. In comparison to “travelling cost is affordable” that got the lowest weighted mean of 2.67 as the verbal interpretation of agree.

The table shows that respondents do not face any difficulties entering the City of Cabanatuan, the tourist sites, goods, and services are accessible to all people—regardless of age, physical restrictions, or disabilities.

AlKahtani et al. (2015) define accessibility as the ability of tourists to conveniently reach a destination, and individual differences among them (e.g., gender, income, and education) may affect the perceptions of accessibility among tourists and their subsequent travel decisions. Ceccato et al. (2020) demonstrated that accessibility can be defined in terms of high geographical connectivity among regions as provided by a smooth

travel experience and efficient transport modes, and designs indices based on tourist perceptions of travel time accessibility.

2.5 Investigating the Tourist Satisfaction of the tourist in terms of Activities.

Table #8 Presenting tourist satisfaction in terms of **Activities**.

Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank	Verbal Description
The activities at the festival are enjoyable, relaxing, and entertaining.	3.28	Strongly Agree	1	Highly in favor
All activities at the festival are suitable for all ages.	3.00	Strongly Agree	4	Highly in favor
The activities at the festival are worth the time, effort, and money spent.	3.11	Strongly Agree	3	Highly in favor
All the activities are remarkable since they show history, cultures, talent, beauty, and craftsmanship.	3.18	Strongly Agree	2	Highly in favor
Average Weighted Mean	3.14			Highly in favor

The total satisfaction of the respondents in terms of activities got average weighted mean of **3.14**. Among the cited items “the activities at the festival are enjoyable, relaxing, and entertaining” got the highest weighted mean of 3.28 verbally interpreted as “**Strongly Agree**”.

However, “All activities at the festival are suitable for all ages” got the lowest average weighted mean of 3.00 has the interpretation of Strongly Agree. Based on the findings respondents are entertained by the events or recreational activities offer by the destination.

Festival guests are seeking uniquely authentic, experientially oriented festivals and events with more meaningful opportunities to participate in activities. They simultaneously seek to satisfy desire for relaxing, and entertainment in esthetically desirable locations. It is more than merely a tourist attraction since they also assist in positive image building for a place (Prentice & Andersen, 2003).

The guests who undergo a positive experience tend to become loyal, long-term, and repeated guests (Cole & Illum, 2006). Festivals also provide a place for tourists to escape from their everyday life, experience enjoyment, and create extraordinary events that can be appreciated alone or shared with others (Morgan & Xu, 2009).

3. Problems encountered by the respondents.

3.1 Problems encountered in terms of Accommodation.

Table #9. Problems with Accommodation.

Accommodations	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
Not too organized	40	3	16.7%
High cost of hotels	129	1	54%
Limited hotels/rooms to stay	70	2	29.3
Total	239		100%

Table 9 shows that 54% or 129 of the frequency of the respondents encountered a high cost of the hotel accommodations. And 70 of the respondents experience limited hotels/ rooms to stay as their problem encountered on the day of the celebration of Bantu Festival. Moreover, 16.7% of the respondents experience not too organized hotels accommodations. A lot of effort has been made in the last decades to reveal, which hotel attributes guest care about. Due to the high costs that are typically involved with investments in the hotel industry, it makes a lot of sense to study. Hotels are one of the most energy intensive facilities, with correspondingly high energy costs. They are ranked among the top five in terms of energy consumption in the

tertiary building sector (Solutions, Citation 2011). During the period up to the date of stay, the room rate may change, and the room might become unavailable if the hotel sells out. With or without reservation, consumers sometimes actively seek better room rates during the period before their arrival to the hotel. That means that for hotel guests, the information search and the evaluation phases could be repeated for the same product (room night) several times before the date of stay.

3.2 Problems encountered in terms of Amenities.

Table #10. Problems with Amenities.

Amenities	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
Crowded parking spaces	114	1	47.7
Limited comfort rooms	66	2	27.63
Unclean surroundings	40	3	16.73
ATM machines are far from destinations	19	4	7.94
Total	239		100%

In

amenities, crowded parking spaces obtain the highest frequency of 114. Limited comfort rooms have 66. While Unclean surrounding has 40 and ATM machines are far from destinations got the lowest vote of 19. Commuters in some busy stretches of roads in the city are having a harrowing time due to the ongoing festival rush. Long traffic snarls and haphazard parking on roadsides are the order of the day. With limited parking space, traffic congestion is expected to grow as the festival season progresses. Several shopkeepers in major market areas say that the civic authorities have failed to provide adequate parking facilities, because of which shoppers often leave without making any purchases. As there is a lack of sufficient parking space in the city, several parts of the city continue to witness long traffic snarls daily as motorists park their vehicles on roadsides. The road space gets narrow due to haphazard parking, thereby hindering smooth flow of traffic stated by Khan M. (2017)

3.4 Problems encountered in terms of Attractions.

Table #11. Problems with Attractions.

Attractions	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
Expensive foods	47	3	19.67
Less attractions	132	1	55.23
Crowded environment	60	2	25.10
Total	239		100%

In attractions, less attractions got the highest vote of 132. Crowded environment has 60 while expensive foods have the lowest vote of 47. According to Jeyamugan (2018). The uniqueness of a place attracts more visitors. Therefore, if there is a variety of natural and cultural attractions the tourers will attach to visit that place again and again. Also, the tourist satisfaction increases if the people who live in that destination are warm welcoming and if there is a variety of food and beverages.

3.5 Problems encountered in terms of Accessibility.

Table #12. Problems with Accessibility.

Accessibility	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
Encountered too much traffic	120	1	50.20
Expensive transportation	45	3	18.8
Road is not in proper condition	74	2	31
Total	239		100%

In accessibility, encountered too much traffic has the highest vote of 120. While road is not in proper condition got 74 and expensive transportation has the lowest vote of 45. As studied by Eck, R. & Montag, D. (2019), special events, including sporting events, concerts, historical reenactments, and fairs and festivals, can generate large volumes of traffic such that congestion and associated problems occur on low-volume roads.

3.6 Problems encountered in terms of Activities.

Table #13. Problems with Activities.

Activities	Frequency	Rank	Percentage
Program start out of time	39	3	16.3
Insufficient space for events	64	2	26.7
Lack of activities that are suitable for all ages	136	1	57
Total	239		100%

In activities, lack of activities that are suitable for all ages got the highest vote of 136. Insufficient space for event has 64 while program start out of time has the lowest vote of 39. Age has frequently been recognized as one of the key attributes and indicators in creating an advertising system. In any case, it has been infrequently discovered the moderating effects of age on the links between attractions and accessibility as well as tourist satisfaction.

According to Omar et al. (2015), age did not influence tourists’ inclination for a specific kind of lodging for delight travel. Nonetheless, others contended that tourist’s age was probably going to fundamentally impact on behaviour pattern and satisfaction (Assaker et al., 2015). There may have indirect effects of tourist age in measuring their satisfaction level (Assaker et al., 2015; Chi, 2011).

4. Summary of the 5A’s of Tourism to the Celebration of Bantu Festival

Table #14. Summary of 5A’s

5A’s of Tourism	Total Average Weighted Mean	Rank
Accommodation	2.95	3
Amenities	2.93	5
Attractions	3.17	1
Accessibility	2.94	4
Activities	3.14	2

Among the 5A’s of tourism, **Attraction** got the highest total average weighted mean of **3.17** and rank **1** of the 5As of tourism. It simply concludes that the tourist attendees of Banatu Festival are satisfied on the **Attraction** that they spot in Cabanatuan City during the celebration.

Particularly, variety of food and beverages in the said destination influenced the satisfaction of the tourist attendees. In Cabanatuan City, there are variety of food and beverage that the respondents can choose from during the celebration of Banatu Festival. The said event location has a diversity of food, specifically both street food and Filipino cuisine offered by the locals that motivates tourist to visit the destination. The variation of refreshment become one of the attractions that Cabanatuan City can offer to its visitors. It has been recognized that food is a main activity or even an important factor in attracting tourists to a location. The desire of the travelers to taste and experience the local cuisine of the location become the motivation to visit a particular tourist destination.

To conclude, among the 5As of tourism Attraction is the most influential factor on the tourist satisfaction to the celebration of Banatu Festival in the Cabanatuan City, Philippines.

5. Proposed Tourism Enhancement Plan addressing the problems encountered by tourist.

The researchers used the data gathered to establish an interpretation that might be contributed to the formulation of the development plan and will serve as a reference for the tourists and the Local Government Unit of Cabanatuan.

Table 15 is the proposed tourism enhancement plan for the industry. It contains different columns. The 1st column is the “Marketing problems” which shows the result of the survey from the respondents; 2nd column refers to the solutions, strategic initiatives, and project that will answer the items on the 1st column, the items presented on this column were the results of the interview or the data gathered from the respondents; 3rd column contains objectives of the strategy or the project related to the problems that need to be addressed; 4th column displays the suggested marketing activities based from the 2nd column; 5th column refers to the budget needed for the implementation of the activity; column 6 displays the players, agencies involve in the strategy or the project who are the responsible persons in the implementation of the activities; 7th column refers to the time frame where the plan should be implemented which refers to the length of the project from the date of its implementation up to the date it will be completed; lastly, the 8th column refers to the signs or signals or measures on how the project was successfully implemented.

Table # 19. Proposed Enhancement Plan

5A's of Tourism	PROBLEMS IN 5A's OF TOURISM	SOLUTION / INTERVENTION	OBJECTIVE OF THE SOLUTION/ INTERVENTION	SUGGESTED MARKETING ACTIVITY	BUDGETARY REQUIREMENTS	PERSONS IN CHARGE	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATOR
Accommodation	1.Providing adequate accommodation is crucial for any tourism destination. However, many destinations struggle to provide enough accommodation in an affordable price to meet the satisfaction of the tourist is a challenge.	1.Promoting alternative accommodations, such as homestays or ecolodges, with much affordable cost compared to hotels accommodation. 2.Establishing more hotels/rooms in the tourist destination	1.Expand the range and quality of accommodation options to meet different tourist needs and budgets. 2. The number of hotels in Cabanatuan are limited so the owner can control the price of accommodation, building more hotels can affect the control power of already established business by forcing them to lower their price to	1. The suggested marketing activity is a social media promotion campaign with the purpose of presenting the other budget friendly accommodation options include hotels, motels, lodges, and homestays.	300,000 Pesos	Owner of Accommodations	3-4 months	1.Monitor the occupancy rates of accommodation facilities collect feedback from guests on their experience and satisfaction with the accommodation options. 2.Evaluate the number of rising accommodation option to ensure there are

			retain and attract new customers					enough accommodations for tourists.
Amenities	1.The said location where the celebration was conducted was lack of parking spaces whereas tourist find it as a major problem in terms of amenities.	1.Developing and implementing regulations to ensure that amenities meet minimum quality and safety standards. 2. For the tourist to have deviance and to avoid the disorganization of the event it recommended to Provide enough space for parking of vehicles.	1. Encourage the development of local businesses to provide amenities and services to tourist. 2. Provide amenities that the tourist needed to ensure their convenience and security.	1. Investing in right amenities and assessing if these amenities are right for your tourist by their feedbacks.	100,000 pesos	Tourism Sites Owner Cabanatuan LGU	1-2 Months	1.Collect data on the availability and quality of basic amenities in tourist areas

Attractions	1.The availability and quality of cultural attractions in the area.	1. Developing and enhancement culturally of the attractions in the location. 2.Encouraging private investment in attraction development through public private relationship.	1.Enhance the cultural attractiveness of the tourist location. 2. Increase the number of quality attractions to the spot and preserve the existing attractions.	1. Providing a unique cultural experience for the tourists.	100,000 pesos	Cabanatuan LGU	2-3 months	Collect data on the number of visitors to each attraction and their feedbacks.
Accessibility	1. The tourist amidst of their travel to the destination encountered too much traffic on their way. 2.Poor infrastructure and transportation systems can make it difficult for tourists to reach their desired destination.	1. Giving the tourist an alternative route to the destination and choosing the right transportation to use. 2. Improving transportation infrastructure and connectivity through investment in roads, and public transportation systems.	1. Improve Transportation options and infrastructure to make destinations more accessible. 2. Make tourist attractions and facilities more accessible to people with disabilities.	1. Providing information, advice and help to the accessibility of the destination it can be on social media platforms.	300,000 pesos	Cabanatuan LGU DPWH	4-5 months	Collect data on the number of tourists using different modes of transportation to access the destination. Monitor the condition and maintenance of transportation infrastructure. Evaluate the accessibility of tourist attractions and facilities to people with disabilities

Activities	1.Major problems encountered by the tourist during the celebration is the lack of activities that are suitable for all ages.	1.Ensuring that activities and attractions meet satisfaction standards of the tourist and are regulated appropriately	1.Increase the range and quality of activities and experiences available to tourists. 2.Promote cultural and heritage activities to showcase the local culture and appropriate to all ages.	1.Effective promotion of the upcoming activities to social media platforms manage by the LGU Cabanatuan.	250,000 pesos	Cabanatuan LGU	2-3 months	Collect data on the number of tourists participating in different activities and experiences
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Based on the findings, the researchers were able to present the following recommendations.

In Cabanatuan City where hotels and accommodations are limited, business owners, enterprises and franchise business offering accommodation should enter the marketplace of Cabatuan City. Potential guest or tourists will be impacted by the awareness of the hotel brand to visit the location if there are enough and affordable accommodations around the destination. Moreover, it will attract many travelers as possible.

The next celebration of Banatu Festival, it is recommended to pursue the activities that bring entertainment to the tourist. Moreover, the researchers recommended to initiate events or activities that suitable for all ages including teenagers and children. Furthermore, in regard to parking space it is recommended to manage and allocate a personnel that will control the parking space for the tourist to experience less hassle and prevent unfortunate events.

In regard to the accessibility of the location, Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) should efficiently maintain the construction of national roads for the access of all Filipinos pursuing economic and social activities in Cabanatuan City. Therefore, fast transportation and comfortable travel will be achieved by the tourists.

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